

UNDERSTANDING CYBER SAFETY BEHAVIOR AMONG TEENAGERS IN GHANA

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Abstract – The development of mobile technology and the expansion of internet access has raised concerns about the cyber safety of teenagers in cyber space. The purpose of this study is to investigate the cyber safety practices, cyber security awareness and teenagers' experiences with cyber-attacks in Ghana. This study adopted a descriptive survey research approach and targeted some public senior high schools in of Ghana. Questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection and it was used to collect data from 153 senior high school students who were conveniently sampled from eight (8) senior high schools in the Ashanti region of Ghana. The results showed that 74.5 percent of teenagers were aware of cybersecurity, 8.7 percent had been involved in cybercrime and their main motivation was either to make money and/or for fun. On the preventive measures against cyber-attacks, 42 percent said they changed their passwords whilst only 1.8 percent said they reported to the police. The cyber-attacks that teenagers often experience are malware attacks and phishing attacks. The study has revealed that these attacks are common among teenagers because they often open unknown email attachments and they fail to regularly update their antiviruses. It is therefore recommended that teenagers be more preventive than corrective in their approach toward cyber-attack. They need to periodically change their passwords and update their antiviruses. The security services should also be more proactive and apprehend perpetrators of cyber-attacks so that victims can have the confidence to report cyber cases to them. It is only in this way that the issue of online crime can be addressed effectively in Ghana.

Keywords – Cyber Safety; Internet; Security; Awareness; Cyber-Attack

I. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of internet access in Ghana is very laudable; considering the huge benefit it brings to individuals, institutions, businesses and the country. As of the third quarter of 2019, Ghana counted about 16.7 million unique mobile subscribers, 15.1 million smartphone devices and 10.7 million mobile internet users in the country [16]. In 2016, Ghana opened a multi-

million dollar 600-rack National Data Centre in Accra, the largest of its kind in West Africa [1]. This goes to confirm the huge investment the government is making to ensure that internet access is available to all of its citizens. In the educational sector, currently, thirteen public tertiary institutions in Ghana are benefiting from a free WiFi pilot project, with the aim that this initiative will soon be rolled out in the over seven hundred and twenty-two public senior high schools in Ghana. These initiatives, though positive, will come at a great cost if research in the cyber safety behavior of our teenagers in the senior high schools is understudied or non-existent.

Cyber safety is defined as the safe and responsible use of information and communication technologies [2] and [3], including protection against unsolicited marketing and advertising [7]. Cyber safety has been a major concern not only in Sub-Saharan Africa but also worldwide. Due to this, the Budapest convention on cybercrime was convinced that as a matter of priority, they need to pursue a common criminal policy aimed at the protection of society against cybercrime, inter alia, by adopting appropriate legislation and fostering international co-operation [5]. Although this convention remains the most significant instrument in this area, especially in protecting young ones against various forms of cybercrime, many nations are yet to take the initiative to adopt it.

As portrayed in a straightforward term, cybercrime is any unlawful action which is perpetrated utilizing any processing gadgets, similar to PC/cell phone [18]. There are various techniques by which digital wrongdoing is carried out, and which incorporates attacks on PC frameworks, cyber-harassing, email spam, phishing, and identity robbery. Cybercrime is the deadliest sort of wrongdoing. It can upset existing set-up within a second [24]. Additionally, cybercrime is characterized as offense that is carried out against individual or group of people with a criminal rationale to purposefully hurt the reputation of the person in question or cause physical or

mental mischief to the casualty directly or by implication, utilizing current media transmission organizations like web and cell phones [9]. Worldwide, teenagers are most susceptible to cyber-attack due to their avid use of the internet and their perceived lack of awareness of cyber security risks. A study conducted by [18] to explore teenager's familiarity with digital protection discovered that about half of the students were aware of digital wrongdoing. A comparable study by [20] discovered that students were tolerably mindful of digital violations and knew about the law against digital wrongdoing. On the other hand, an investigation led by [19] showed that a large number of secondary school students shared their private information online and did not know about the likely misuse of such information by cyber criminals.

The reason for increase in cybercrime owes to the fact that perpetrators gain easy access to mobile devices, the internet and network facilities [21]. Adopting a descriptive research design to survey 44,500 university undergraduate students in Nigeria, [17] found that students engage in online drug trafficking, cyber stalking, email hack, hacking of organizational accounts, identity theft, among others. The students in their various responses showed that they had been involved in one form of cybercrime or the other in their various institutions. [15] further explained that most of these students were deeply involved in cybercrime alongside their counterparts in the school. [6] disagreed vehemently with the finding of this study when he found out that undergraduates are fully occupied with academic and vocational activities that can make them associate with cyber theft.

On the issue of teenagers' experience with cyber - attack, a study by [11] conducted on a sample of more than 200 Slovenian Internet users revealed that 83% of respondents had experienced a computer virus infection. He also reported that just under one third of respondents' friends experienced computer hacking and online identity theft and that they reported knowing at least one person who was harmed by cybercrime. Thus, the forms of harassments the perpetrators of cyber bullying exhibit comes in different faces. The nature of harassment ranges from ignoring, disrespecting, threatening, calling names, spreading rumors, email bombing, picking on and ridiculing [22] to hiding names while sending SMS or when in a chat room, kicking someone out of a chat room, and violating the privacy of someone by a webcam [23].

On the preventive measure teenagers take to curb cyber-attacks, [13] mentioned the importance of cyber security training programs that can change the attitude and behavior of internet users, by decreasing the number

of risk affiliated with cyber security incidents. They also pointed out the need for appropriate security practices that will change the behavior of online users in their day-to-day practice. [11] reported that approximately one half of respondents have sufficient information to protect their devices misuse or personal data/theft. However, it turned out that 40% of them did not know or did not install any software protection on their Internet-connected devices (computer, phone, etc.). [25] also showed that internet users possess adequate cyber threat awareness but apply only minimal protective measures usually relatively common and simple ones.

[10] reported that respondents' behaviors towards curbing cyberattacks was ambivalent. On one hand, they argued that they know how to behave in the case of a cyberattack ($M=3.10$, $SD=1.19$). For example, they indicated that they would not provide information on the web ($M=2.42$, $SD=0.93$). In addition, they argued that their length of a standard password is 10 on the average, which was considered to them as safe. On the other hand, when asked to describe how they acted in order to protect their computer, they only indicated 4 measures on average out of 11 options. This indicated their uncertain posture towards cyber safety. Hence, [4] asserted that the primary tool for such prevention is undoubtedly education aimed at establishing greater awareness and knowledge regarding illegal internet content and cybercrime among children and teenagers, as well as parents and educators. Thus, Cyber violence is a relatively new phenomenon, with most of the reports emerging through publicity in the mass media. In the same vein, there should be a mandatory prevention-education on cybercrime and cyber safety for all incoming students [12].

A number of studies have been conducted to assess the causes and effects of cyber threats [8]. This is an indication of the increasing prominence of cyber-attacks among organizations and citizens all over the world. Despite the growing interest and impact of cyber-attacks on teenagers, there still remains a general lack of education on cyber security among the consuming Ghanaian public [14]. It is for this reason that the researcher decided to carry out this research to understand the cyber behavior of teenagers on the internet. Hence, these questions are formulated to form the basis of this study:

1. What is the level of awareness of cyber security among teenagers?
2. To what extent are teenagers involved in cybercrime?
3. How often do teenagers experience cyberattacks?

4. What preventive measures have teenagers put in place to prevent cyberattacks?

A. Research Objectives

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. To understand the cyber security awareness among teenagers.
2. To explore the extent to which teenagers are involved in cybercrime.
3. To find out how often teenagers experience cyberattacks.
4. To identify the preventive measures teenagers have put in place to prevent cyberattacks.

B. Purpose of the study

The study seeks to investigate the cyber safety practices, teenagers’ experiences with cyber-attacks, their cyber security awareness and preventive measures taken by teenagers in Ghana to curb cyber-attacks.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design incorporating quantitative research approach with a researcher-made questionnaire as the instrument. The population of the study was all form two (2) students in eight senior high schools in Ashanti Region. The sampling technique used was convenience sampling since the researcher was supervising students on teaching practice in that region. In all, 153 students were selected from the eight schools. Questionnaire was administered by the researcher himself and was completed on the spot by all respondents. Thus, the return rate was 100%. Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) was used for the analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Cybersecurity Awareness among Teenagers

Fig. 1 represents students’ responses on the question on their awareness of cyber security. Out of the 153 respondents, 152 responded whereas only 1 respondent did not respond to the question. 114 students representing 74.5% said they are aware of cybersecurity, 27 students representing 17.6% said they are not aware of cybersecurity whereas 11 representing 7.2% responded that they are not sure. From the above, we can confidently conclude that most teenagers are very much aware of cybersecurity. This finding confirms the study made by [18] that about half of the students knew about digital wrongdoings.

Figure 1. Awareness of Cyber Security

B. Extent to which Teenagers are Involved in Cybercrime

Students were further asked about the extent to which they are involved in cybercrime. The cross tabulation in Table I clearly shows that 13 students have been involved in cybercrime, 130 students have not been involved in cybercrime whereas 6 students stated they were not sure whether they had been involved or not. Thus, from the findings, majority (130) representing 87.2% of the respondents have not been involved in cybercrime. Thus, the findings are in line with the argument by [6] when he disagreed in his findings that students are fully occupied with academic and vocational activities which occupies them from engaging in cyber theft. However, [17] and [15] concluded from their findings that most students engage in various forms of cybercrimes.

TABLE I. TEENAGERS INVOLVEMENT IN CYBER CRIME

Age group	Have you been involved in any form of cybercrime before			Total
	Yes	No	Not sure	
10-20	6	44	3	53
16-20	7	84	3	94
21-25	0	2	0	2
Total	13	130	6	149

Furthermore, the students were asked to state their reasons for their involvement in cybercrime. The results from Table II showed that 5 of the teenagers said they were involved in cybercrime to make money and for fun whereas 1 teenager got involved out of ignorance. None of the students were involved in cybercrime due to pressure from friends nor to retaliate.

TABLE II. REASONS FOR INVOLVING IN CYBER CRIME

What was your motivation for getting involved	Frequency
To make money	5
For fun	5
Ignorance	1
Pressure from friends	0
To retaliate	0
Total	11

C. How Often Teenagers Experience Cyberattacks

From Table III, it can be seen that most of the respondents between the frequencies of 43 and 55 concluded that they have never experienced cyberattacks whereas another group which are between the frequency of 4 and 28 indicated that they experienced cyberattack once a while. From the responses, there is an indication that students generally do not experience cyberattacks and for those who do, they often get malware and phishing attacks. Thus, this finding does not confirm the studies by [23] when they found out that there is a higher rate of cyber bullying among public school students. However, the findings are in line with [11] who found that 83% of respondents had experienced a computer virus infection.

TABLE III. RATE OF CYBERATTACKS

Cyber attacks	N/A	Daily	Once a week	Once a month	Once in a while	Never
Malware attacks (viruses, worms, Trojan horses etc.)	5	8	6	3	28	43

Unauthorized access of confidential information like email and other school related documents	6	5	1	2	10	44
Stealing passwords to access accounts	7	5	1	3	25	50
Identity theft and impersonation	6	1	0	1	4	55
Phishing emails	5	6	0	2	13	50
Online fraud	4	7	1	4	13	54

D. Preventive Measures Against Cyberattacks

Fig. 2 is a chart to represent exactly the data in Table IV. From Table IV and Fig. 2, one can conclude that most students use strong passwords to prevent cyberattacks and this represent a frequency of 47 which is a valid percentage of 28%. Also, on the issue of malware protection, it was realized that only 12.4% regularly scan their computers for malwares and out of this, only 10.5% regularly updated their antiviruses. Unfortunately, only a minimal 4.6% of the respondents do not open unknown email attachment. This study confirms the study by [25] who found out that internet users possess adequate cyber threat awareness but apply only minimal protective measures usually relatively common and simple ones in cyber space. As opined by

[13], training of students at a younger age about cyber-attacks and involving them in discussions about cyber bullying will make them aware of cyber security and devise means and ways to stop such attacks and always remain safe and secured on the internet.

TABLE IV. PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST CYBER ATTACKS

Preventive Measure	Frequency	Percentage
Use a mixture of lower- and upper-case alphabets, numbers and symbols for password	41	26.8
Regularly update antiviruses	16	10.5
Regularly update my operating system	12	7.8
Regularly scan computer for viruses and other forms of malware	19	12.4
Do not write/disclose password to anybody	12	7.8
Prevents others from looking over shoulder to view login password	7	4.6
Do not leave default password in use	5	3.3
Change password frequently	8	5.2
Do not open an unknown email attachment	7	4.6
Do not allow others to work in your computer account	5	3.3
Missing System	21	13.7
Total	153	100.0

Figure 2. Preventive Measures Against Cyber Attacks

Furthermore, when the students were asked about the actions they take when they experience a cyber-attack and/or cyber bullying, 30.7 percent reported that they changed their password whereas 12.4 percent indicated they did not tell anyone about it and blocked their accounts. Just 1.3 percent reported to the police about cyber-attacks and/or cyber bullying. These results are presented in Table 5. Thus, in line with these findings, [13] opined that individuals facing cyberattacks should report the behavior to the appropriate institutions, and block their accounts. [10] also found that their length of a standard password is around 10 on average which is considered by them as safe.

TABLE V. ACTIONS TAKEN ON CYBERATTACK / CYBERBULLYING EXPERIENCE

Action taken	Frequency	Percent (%)
Report to police	2	1.3
Report to parent	6	3.9
Report to your teacher	5	3.3
Report to website administrator /telephone company	14	9.2
You didn't tell anyone	19	12.4

Changed password	47	30.7
Blocked your account	19	12.4
Missing System	41	26.8
Total	153	100.0

IV. CONCLUSION

It is clear from the study that cybersecurity awareness among teenagers in Ghana is high. A very few teenagers are involved in cyber-attacks for the purposes of making money and for fun. The cyber-attacks that teenagers often face are malware attacks and phishing attacks. The study has revealed that these attacks are common among teenagers because they often open unknown email attachments and they fail to regularly update their antiviruses. Again, it has been observed that teenagers change their passwords after they have experienced cyber-attacks. It is therefore recommended that teenagers be more preventive than corrective in their approach toward cyber-attack. They need to periodically change their passwords and update their antiviruses. Although cyber safety has not traditionally been part of the senior high school curriculum, the changing nature of society, in particular the increased use of ICT now justifies its inclusion. Rather than seeing cyber-attack as a reason to deny students access to ICT, the Ministry of Education should regard its increased use as an opportunity to impart safe and responsible practices to students so that they become ethical cybercitizens of the future. Also, the Government of Ghana in conjunction with the security services should develop a national cyber security framework that specifies cyber security requirement controls for individual network users. If approaches towards preventing cybercrime are to be truly effective, the security services should be more proactive and apprehend perpetrators of cyber-attacks so that victims can have the confidence to report cyber cases to them. It is only in this way that the issue of online crime can be addressed effectively.

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